

CLARIN in EU Projects

CLARIN ERIC, together with its national nodes, participates in EU-funded projects that are relevant to its vision and mission, such as in the Horizon 2020 programme or as part of Horizon Europe. CLARIN is currently active in the following EU-funded projects:

FAIRCORE4EOSC

The **FAIRCORE4EOSC** project focuses on the development and realisation of core components for EOSC, supporting a FAIR EOSC and addressing gaps identified in the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). Leveraging existing technologies and services, the project will develop nine new EOSC core components aimed at improving the discoverability and interoperability of an increased amount of research outputs.

June 2022 – May 2025

eosc | Focus

EOSC Focus supports the EOSC Partnership in delivering its mission of establishing Open Science as the ‘new normal’ and achieving the ambitious goals set in the EOSC Co-Programmed Partnership Memorandum of Understanding. The project will also offer coordination and operational support to the EOSC Association Task Forces and will work in collaboration with the EOSC Association Board of Directors to advance the EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) and the EOSC monitoring framework.

June 2022 – May 2025

ERIC FORUM

Following the successful set-up and implementation of the ERIC Forum, the **ERIC Forum 2** project aims to structure the cooperation between ERICs, support the implementation of ERIC Regulation and ERIC services, and consolidate the integration of the ERICs in the European Research Area by deepening the ERIC Forum’s contribution to research policies.

September 2023 – August 2027

ATRIUM

The **ATRIUM** (Advancing Frontier Research In the Arts and Humanities) project bridges four leading European Research Infrastructures in the arts and humanities domain: ARIADNE, CLARIN, DARIAH and OPERAS. ATRIUM aims to empower arts and humanities scholars in their use of digital methods by facilitating access to a wide range of reusable workflows and interoperable, composable services.

January 2024 – December 2027

OSCARS aims to foster the uptake of Open Science in Europe by consolidating the achievements of leading European RIs in the ESFRI roadmap into interdisciplinary FAIR data services and working practices. OSCARS will strengthen the role of the Science Clusters in the European Research Area by developing Community-based Competence Centres and Composable Open Data and Analysis Services, data processing and management solutions, and by supporting Open Science projects and services funded through a cascading-grant mechanism.

January 2024 – December 2027

Open Science Trails (**OSTrails**) focuses on enhancing the planning, tracking, and assessing of scientific knowledge production. By collaborating with service providers and research communities across countries and domains, it aims to streamline FAIRness, interconnectivity and machine actionability that improve and extend existing Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystems and align them with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

February 2024 – January 2027

ECHOES (European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science) aims to create the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) as a shared platform for heritage professionals and researchers to access data, scientific and training resources, and advanced digital tools co-developed by the heritage community according to their specific needs. ECHOES will bring together fragmented communities of the Cultural Heritage field into a new community around the Digital Commons.

June 2024 – June 2029

Learn more about CLARIN's role in EU projects on our website!

